

METHOD OF ANTI-RISK MANAGEMENT IN IT AUDIT PROJECTS

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Abstract

A review of current approaches to risk management of IT audit projects is conducted. Stages of anti-risk management of IT audit projects are defined and the method of anti-risk management of IT audit projects is developed. The possible states of opportunities interaction system and risks threats in IT audit projects are mathematically described, according to the probable balances values of such risks. It is determined that according to interaction system state of risks' opportunities and threats in IT audit projects, risks can be divided into three groups: threatening, harmonized and chance.

Keywords: IT audit projects; IT audit project management; project risks; risk management of IT-audit projects.

Introduction. In a relatively short period of time, the field of information technology (IT) from the ordinary, has become one of the main drivers of the world economy. The number of IT specialists in the country is growing rapidly: from 89 thousand professionals in 2015 to 190 thousand in 2019 [1]. The main share of the global IT market is in the United States (36.8%), followed by China (11.3%) and the United Kingdom (5.8%). According to the Top Lead directory, we are competing with Romania and Poland in terms of market size, significantly behind India and China.

Ukraine is attractive for the development of IT business among countries with developed economies. Firstly, the labor markets in Poland and Romania are already significantly "overheated". Secondly, taxation is very profitable in Ukraine. Thirdly, competence and cultural proximity place Ukrainian developers far above Indian ones. Today, Ukrainians can create, promote and sell IT products in global markets. They are interested not only in creating a product, but also in its active development. The Ukrainian IT industry is currently successfully competing in the global market and is a reliable source of foreign exchange earnings. For productive and efficient work of IT enterprises requires constant monitoring and control of the real state of IT infrastructure. Therefore, an IT audit is introduced to assess the state of the information and / or financial system of the enterprise. Conducting an IT audit is a starting point and allows to objectively assess the current relevance of the IT infrastructure, compliance with business requirements, use of both

financial and human resources, as well as draw conclusions about changes or upgrades to this system [2].

V. Rudnytsky, O. Pugachenko, S. Kanygin, R. Us, S. Golov, B. Usach, V. Zhuk, Yu. Prozorov, V. Galkin, M. Bilukha, I. Platonova, A. Kuzminsky, N. Dorosh and others are engaged in research of development of audit. I. Platonova [3], N. Kuzhelny, E. Petryk [4], F. Butynets [5], G. Davydov dedicate their research to the issues of development, audit organization and point to a certain completion of the formation of the national audit system. O. Redko analyzes performance indicators of the audit services market, N. Dorosh researches the organization of auditing activities and pays attention to the quality control of the audit services market, I. Pilipenko believes that it is necessary to improve the regulatory framework, which regulates auditing activities. The author [3] distinguishes audit by the nature of the audit: confirmatory, system-oriented and risk-based or risk-oriented audit, and in the source [6] there are: investment, external, internal and special types of audit (environmental, energy audit, project audit and information security audit).

Some theoretical and applied aspects of solving problems in the activities of project-oriented IT enterprises are presented in the works of A. Biloshchytsky, S. Bushuyev, N. Bushuyeva, R. Druzhinin, I. Kononenko, O. Medvedeva, D. Novikov, V. Racha, Archibald, I. Babayev, V. Bykov, E. Reshke, H. Tanaka, Y. Tesla, S. Tsyutsyuri, H. Shelle, S. Chernova, O. Voitenko, N. Yegorchenkova, Z. Stashevsky, Y. Borzov and others.

The author [7] notes that the information support of internal audit at an industrial enterprise is the main condition for effective prevention and timely detection and elimination of errors, as it provides verification, modeling and analysis of data to establish their completeness, quality, legality and reliability, and improving the efficiency of financial and economic activities at the enterprise during the internal audit is possible due to the effective information support for the provision of relevant information and control functions in the relevant accounting system. Assessment of economic security of investment projects for enterprise informatization was carried out by the authors [8], the role of audit in detecting fraudulent actions with financial statements noted in [9].

Problems of staff motivation in the IT sphere, basic and modern theories of motivation are presented by the authors [10]. Projects in the field of IT through the prism of soft projects were considered by O. Medvedeva in [11], features of personnel management in the IT field in [12], where the basic requirements to the knowledge and skills of HR-manager and IT-recruiter are given, the sources of search for qualified specialists for IT companies are considered, the functional capabilities of HRM-systems are characterized. The method of evaluating the team of IT-project executors in which it is proposed to consider the task of appointing employees to work on a new IT-project as a kind of clustering task, proposed in [13]. Integrated application of emotional intelligence and KANBAN method in IT project management is described in the source [14].

The impact of internal audit principles on the control environment: economic and social consequences studied by the author [15] and proved that the whole set of methods, ways, techniques used in the internal audit process provide unity and logic methodological principles, and compliance with organizational principles allows to choose the most optimal options for streamlining the structure and operation of the internal audit department.

Models and mechanisms for planning the content of educational projects of higher educational institutions of the State Service of Ukraine for Emergencies and monitoring the process of competence formation of IT projects of the State Service of Ukraine for Emergencies in Information Security on the basis of competence approach according to customer requirements are proposed in the source [16], and the mathematical model of the educational project of the State Service of Ukraine for Emergencies of training a specialist in the field of information security is considered in [17].

IT audits are a key component to ensure the quality of enterprise management, without reliable information systems and effective IT control measures, it is unable to properly perform operations / transactions and summarize reliable financial reporting, which, in turn, affects the level of achievement of its objectives and goals.

Based on the sources [18-19], the IT audit project (ITAP) is a set of interrelated measures to verify the accounting data of the financial statements of the IT

company and conducting an assessment of IT infrastructure, aimed at creating a unique product: independent opinions of the auditor, findings, evidences, conclusions and recommendations on all material aspects and in accordance with applicable laws, regulations (standards) or other rules, and in accordance with the requirements of users in terms of time and resource constraints.

Such a comprehensive inspection of the condition, allows to identify opportunities and shortcomings of the existing information infrastructure at the enterprise, its compliance with the requirements and expectations of management, allows to assess the likely development of business and communication processes at the enterprise [20]. Modernization or modification of existing systems or operational solutions can be carried out only in the presence of full data on the current state of the company's IT management.

Tasks, principles, stages and features of ITAP, as well as the characteristics of its product are pre-defined by the authors in the sources [18, 21].

According to sources [18, 22, 23], ITAP management is a process of management and coordination of human, material and financial resources during the project life cycle by applying modern management methods and techniques to achieve project results in terms of composition and scope of work, cost, time, quality and satisfaction of project stakeholders. ITAP management is based on a systems approach. It is implemented by the project team. The methods of project analysis are used as a component in the project management process.

Risk management is currently used as the main method of combating deviations and uncertainties in the project. A large number of works and developments are devoted to this issue. Among them are Ukrainian (S. Bushuyev, N. Bushuyeva, Y. Tesla, S. Chernov, K. Koshkin, E. Druzhinin, O. Danchenko, Y. Kharitonov, I. Semko, D. Bedriy, K. Kolotyryna, O. Savina) and foreign scholars (Drucker Peter F., J. M. Keynes, G. Simon, A. Tovba, G. Tsipes, V. Shapiro, etc.)

Risk-oriented IT audit, according to [24] - is an activity carried out in the interests of management, which collects audit evidence and assesses their compliance with agreed audit criteria in order to form an independent expert assessment of the actual level of IT risks and make recommendations aimed at their minimization.

According to the analysis of recent publications and research, the degree of study of the problem by domestic and foreign scientists cannot be considered sufficient, and the problem of forming a holistic ITAP management methodology, taking into account their specifics, requires further research.

Main part. ITAPs have specific risks that synthesize components of organizational risks, IT risks and the risks posed by stakeholders. Based on the source [18], it can be argued that a significant part of the deviations and uncertainties that lead to increased time and cost are directly related to the stakeholders of projects. Each of the stakeholders has the opportunity to influence the project in the best way, or hinder its implementation. However, sometimes having positive

guidelines and goals, they can create wrong or unnecessary actions at the moment and, thus, pose a threat. But, and sometimes vice versa, when high-risk projects lead to increased opportunities and chances of high efficiency and success of the project. Opposites of opportunity-threat complement each other: opportunities create threats, and threats give opportunities, and only in a balanced harmonious relationship can achieve the right and effective result [18] through risk management.

The essence of the model is that ITAP risk management is integrated by minimizing the risks of IT audit by applying risk management to major project stakeholders by project managers and top managers, which ultimately improves the efficiency of the company by reducing project cost, time for implementation, quality improving of such projects, and leads to ensuring the implementation of strategic goals of the company.

Each stakeholder group has its influence on the project implementation, and the impact can be positive (chance), negative (threatening) or neutral [25]. The positive impact of stakeholders on the project is useful as it helps to implement the project. However, it can also have negative consequences. Negative impact, in general, is not useful during project implementation. However, sometimes the opposite can happen. Neutral influence, in general, does not affect the implementation of the project, however, sometimes it can be changed by external factors, and then from neutral can be transformed to either positive or negative. It is important for the project manager and the project team not to miss the transformation of neutral influence into negative, or to make efforts to change the neutral position to a positive one. Due to their opposition, opportunities and threats, being antipolar, are mutually opposed and limit each other. When one side is in excess, the other

is deficient. When one side is weakened, the other is strengthened. To ensure effective management of project stakeholders, it is necessary to balance their risks: increase the opportunities for positive impact of stakeholders and reduce the chances of threats, while maintaining a stable state of the system, within three categories that correspond to the "magic" triangle of project management goals: time, cost, quality, which is possible by combining the techniques of opportunity management (chance management) and threats (risk management) [25].

ITAP risk management is based on stakeholder management of wind energy projects, described in the source [26], and supplemented by taking into account the positive and negative consequences of organizational risks and IT risks inherent in these projects. As a result, it allows in-depth study of ITAP, identification of high risks, to further reduce them and make reasonable management decisions, which contributes to achieving the goals of ITAP.

The scheme of the ITAP risk management method is presented in Figure 1.

Based on the features of ITAP, the specifics of their management, the proposed conceptual model and risk management ITAP and based on the mathematical model of management of stakeholders of wind energy projects, described in [26], a mathematical model of ITAP risk management can be developed.

Mathematical apparatus can be used, in particular: methods of set theory, systems analysis, risk balances, etc., to describe possible states of the ITAP risk interaction system.

First, the company's IT risks, organizational risks and project stakeholders are identified through the prism of threats and opportunities, and three sets are obtained:

Fig. 1. Scheme of the method of ITAP risk management

Set of the company's IT risks $\{ITR\}$:
 $ITR = \{ITR_1; \dots; ITR_w; \dots; ITR_x\}$

where x

– the amount of IT risks in the company, w
 – IT risk number, ($x = \overline{1; w}$).

Set of the company's organizational risks $\{OR\}$:

$$OR = \{OR_1; \dots; OR_y; \dots; OR_z\}$$

where z – the amount of organizational risks,
 y – organizational risk number, ($y = \overline{1; z}$).

Set of the company's stakeholders $\{RS\}$:

$$RS = \{RS_1; \dots; RS_r; \dots; RS_c\}$$

where c – the amount of company's stakeholders,
 r – stakeholder number, ($r = \overline{1; c}$).

Of the three sets of risks (company's IT risks $\{ITR\}$, organizational risks $\{OR\}$ and risks of project's stakeholders $\{RS\}$) we choose the risks inherent in ITAP and get a set of ITAP risks $\{R_{ITAP}\}$:

$$R_{ITAP} = \{R^{IT}\} \cap \{R^O\} \cap \{S\}$$

where R^{IT} – set of IT risks, R^O – set of organizational risks, S – set of ITAP stakeholders.

Thus, we will assess the magnitude of these risks.

Set of ITAP IT risks $\{R^{IT}\}$:

$$R^{IT} = \{R_1^{IT}; \dots; R_a^{IT}; \dots; R_b^{IT}\},$$

where b

– the amount of ITAP IT risks, a – IT risk number, ($a = \overline{1; b}$).

Set of organizational risks $\{R^O\}$:

$$R^O = \{R_1^O; \dots; R_e^O; \dots; R_f^O\},$$

where f – the amount of organizational risks,
 e – organizational risk number, ($e = \overline{1; f}$).

Set of ITAP stakeholders, S (Stakeholders):

$$S = \{S_1; \dots; S_k; \dots; S_l\},$$

where l – the amount of ITAP stakeholders,
 k – stakeholder number, ($k = \overline{1; l}$).

Based on the conceptual model of risk balance (opportunities and threats) of stakeholders of wind energy projects [25], to ensure effective risk management it is necessary to balance them: increase opportunities for positive impact and reduce the possibility of threats. Therefore, it is first necessary to identify opportunities and threats to certain sets of ITAP risks.

The set of opportunities in ITAP IT risk is denoted as C^{IT} (Chance):

$$C^{IT} = \{C_{a1}^{IT}; \dots; C_{ag}^{IT}; \dots; C_{ah}^{IT}\},$$

where C_{ag}^{IT} – possibility of a -th IT risk; h – the number of opportunities for IT risks, g – the number of opportunity for the a – th IT risk, ($g = \overline{1; h}$).

Possibility of a -th IT risk C_{ag}^{IT} are defined by the formula:

$$C_{ag}^{IT} = \sum_{g=1}^h P_{ag} \cdot V_{ag}, \quad (1)$$

where P_{ag} – the probability of a -th opportunity of IT risk; V_{ag} – gain from the a -th opportunity, UAH, h – the amount of IT risk opportunities.

The set of threats in ITAP IT risks is denoted as D^{IT} (Danger):

$$D^{IT} = \{D_{a1}^{IT}; \dots; D_{ap}^{IT}; \dots; D_{aq}^{IT}\},$$

where D_{ap}^{IT} – threat of a -th IT risk, q – the amount of threats, p – the number of threat of a -th IT risk, ($p = \overline{1; q}$).

Threats of a -th IT risks in ITAP D_{ap}^{IT} are defined by the formula:

$$D_{ap}^{IT} = \sum_{p=1}^q P_{ap} \cdot V_{ap}, \quad (2)$$

where P_{ap} – the probability of the p -th threat; V_{ap} – losses from the p -th threat, UAH, q – the amount of ITAP IT risk threats.

The set of opportunities for organizational risks is denoted as C^O :

$$C^O = \{C_{e1}^O; \dots; C_{es}^O; \dots; C_{et}^O\},$$

where C_{es}^O – opportunity of e -th organizational risk; t – the amount of opportunities for organizational risk, s – number of e – th opportunity of organizational risk, ($s = \overline{1; t}$).

The possibility of e -th organizational risk C_{es}^O are defined by the formula:

$$C_{es}^O = \sum_{s=1}^t P_{es} \cdot V_{es}, \quad (3)$$

where P_{es} – the probability of the s -th opportunity of e -th organizational risk; V_{es} – gain from the s -th opportunity, UAH, t – the amount of opportunities for organizational risk.

The set of organizational risk threats in ITAP is denoted as D^O :

$$D^O = \{D_{e1}^O; \dots; D_{eu}^O; \dots; D_{ev}^O\},$$

where D_{eu}^O – threat of e -th organizational risk, v – the amount of threats, u – threat number of e -th organizational risk, ($u = \overline{1; v}$).

Threats of e -th organizational risk D_{eu}^O are defined by the formula:

$$D_{eu}^O = \sum_{u=1}^v P_{eu} \cdot V_{eu}, \quad (4)$$

where P_{eu} – the probability of the u -th threat; V_{eu} – losses from the u -th threat, UAH, v – the amount of organizational risk threats.

The set of opportunities of ITAP stakeholders is denoted as C :

$$C_k = \{C_{k1}; \dots; C_{ki}; \dots; C_{kn}\},$$

where C_{ki} – opportunity of the k -th ITAP stakeholder; n – the amount of stakeholder opportunities, i – opportunity number of the k – th stakeholder, ($i = \overline{1; n}$).

Opportunity of the k -th stakeholder ITAP C_{ki} can be defined by the formula:

$$C_{ki} = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ki} \cdot V_{ki}, \quad (5)$$

where P_{ki} – the probability of the i -th opportunity of an ITAP stakeholder; V_{ki} – gain from the i -th opportunity, UAH, n – the amount of opportunities for the stakeholder.

The set of threats to ITAP stakeholders is denoted as D :

$$D_k = \{D_{k1}; \dots; D_{kj}; \dots; D_{km}\},$$

where D_{kj} – threat to the k -th ITAP stakeholder, m – the amount of stakeholder threats, j – opportunity number of the k -th stakeholder, ($j = \overline{1; m}$).

Threats of the k -th ITAP stakeholder D_{kj} can be defined by the formula:

$$D_{kj} = \sum_{j=1}^m P_{kj} \cdot V_{kj}, \quad (6)$$

where P_{kj} – the probability of the j -th threat; V_{kj} – losses from the j -th threat, UAH, m – the amount of stakeholder threats.

The set of balances of risks (opportunities and threats) is denoted as BR (Balance of risk).

Then, set of ITAP IT risk balances:

$$BR^{IT} = \{BR_1^{IT}; \dots; BR_a^{IT}; \dots; BR_b^{IT}\},$$

where BR_a^{IT} – a -th IT risk balance, b – the amount of IT risks, a – IT risk number, ($a = \overline{1; b}$).

Based on the conceptual model of risk balance (opportunities and threats) of stakeholders [25] the value of a -th IT risk balance BR_a^{IT} can be defined by the formula:

$$BR_a^{IT} = \sum_{g=1}^h C_{ag}^{IT} + \sum_{p=1}^q D_{ap}^{IT}, \quad (7)$$

Based on formula (1) and formula (2), the balance of the a -th IT risk BR_a^{IT} will have next vision:

$$BR_a^{IT} = \sum_{g=1}^h P_{ag} \cdot V_{ag} + \sum_{p=1}^q P_{ap} \cdot V_{ap} \quad (8)$$

The set of balances of company's organizational risks:

$$BR^O = \{BR_1^O; \dots; BR_e^O; \dots; BR_f^O\},$$

where BR_e^O – balance of e -th organizational risk, f – the amount of organizational risks, e – organizational risk number, ($e = \overline{1; f}$).

The value of the balance of e -th organizational risk BR_e^O can be defined by the formula:

$$BR_e^O = \sum_{s=1}^t C_{es}^O + \sum_{u=1}^v D_{eu}^O \quad (9)$$

Based on formula (3) and formula (4), the value of the balance of e -th organizational risk BR_e^O will have next vision:

$$BR_e^O = \sum_{s=1}^t P_{es} \cdot V_{es} + \sum_{u=1}^v P_{eu} \cdot V_{eu} \quad (10)$$

The set of risk balances (opportunities and threats) of ITAP stakeholders is denoted as BR :

$$BR = \{BR_1; \dots; BR_k; \dots; BR_l\},$$

where BR_k – risk balance for the k -th ITAP stakeholder, l – the amount of ITAP stakeholders, k – stakeholder number, ($k = \overline{1; l}$).

The value of the risk balance BR_k for the k -th ITAP stakeholder can be defined by the formula:

$$BR_k = \sum_{i=1}^n C_{ki} + \sum_{j=1}^m D_{kj}, \quad (11)$$

Based on formula (5) and formula (6), the value of the risk balance BR_k for the k -th ITAP stakeholder will have next vision:

$$BR_k = \sum_{i=1}^n P_{ki} \cdot V_{ki} + \sum_{j=1}^m P_{kj} \cdot V_{kj} \quad (12)$$

Given the possible states of interaction system of opportunities and threats at source [25], the value of the risk balance (BR) can be:

$$BR_k = \begin{cases} BR < 0, \text{ якщо } C < D \\ BR = 0, \text{ якщо } C = D \\ BR > 0, \text{ якщо } C > D, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where C – the total amount of opportunities for the corresponding risk, and D – the total amount of threats of the corresponding risk.

According to the conceptual model of risk balance (opportunities and threats) [25] and to IT risk balances, risks, organizational risks and all ITAP stakeholders are divided into three groups:

- if $BR < 0$ – threatening, with high threats and low opportunities;
- if $BR = 0$ – harmonized, in which opportunities and threats are in equilibrium;
- if $BR > 0$ – chances, with high opportunities and low threats.

Based on the results obtained, we can determine, respectively, three sets for each type of ITAP risk.

The set of IT risks, $\{R^{IT}\}$, can be defined by the formula:

$$R^{IT} = \{R^{IT}_D\} \cup \{R^{IT}_G\} \cup \{R^{IT}_C\},$$

where R^{IT}_D – set of threatening IT risks; R^{IT}_G – set of harmonized IT risks; R^{IT}_C – set of chance IT risks.

The set of organizational risks, $\{R^O\}$, can be represented by a formula:

$$R^O = \{R^O_D\} \cup \{R^O_G\} \cup \{R^O_C\},$$

where R^O_D – the set of threatening organizational risks; R^O_G – the set of harmonized organizational risks; R^O_C – the set of chance organizational risks.

The set of ITAP stakeholders, S , can be represented by a formula:

$$S = \{S_D\} \cup \{S_G\} \cup \{S_C\},$$

where S_D – the set of threatening ITAP stakeholders; S_G – the set of harmonized ITAP stakeholders; S_C – the set of chance ITAP stakeholders.

Then, the overall set of high (threatening) ITAP risks $\{R_{ITAP}^{high}\}$ will look like this:

$$R_{ITAP}^{high} = \{R_D^{IT}\} \cup \{R_D^O\} \cup \{S_D\}$$

where $\{R_D^{IT}\}$ – the set of threatening IT risks; $\{R_D^O\}$ – the set of threatening organizational risks, $\{S_D\}$ – the set of threatening ITAP stakeholders.

For each threatening set, it can be conducted an additional assessment of opportunities and threats within the set or for each stakeholder individually, which allows in-depth research of risk components (opportunities and threats) and expands the boundaries of management decisions.

Chance risks need to be kept and encouraged, harmonized risks need to be worked on to increase the capacity component, and threatening risks need to be reduced to an acceptable level.

Conclusions. In the process of managing IT audit projects, the management is faced with the question of the feasibility and effectiveness of their implementation, which requires adapted to the IT sector models, methods and mechanisms and clear algorithms for their use. The article identifies the stages of ITAP risk management, describes the mathematical model of such management, which allows to assess their capabilities and threats, determine the size of risk balances, rate risk assessment of ITAP and stakeholders on these balances and form sets of threatening, harmonized and chance risks; and identify the set of high risks of ITAP. Further research should focus on the impact of risk balances on the effectiveness of ITAP management within three categories that correspond to the "magic" triangle of project management objectives: time, cost, quality.

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КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНІ ЗАСАДИ ФОРМУВАННЯ ТА РЕАЛІЗАЦІЇ СТАЛОГО РОЗВИТКУ УКРАЇНИ

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CONCEPTUAL PRINCIPLES OF FORMATION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF UKRAINE

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Анотація

У статті досліджується поточний стан реалізації «Концепції сталого розвитку України». Наголошується на важливості даної Концепції як визначальної в умовах розвитку та адаптації української економіки до вимог світового ринку задля підвищення конкурентоспроможності і набуття ознак сталості.

У публікації розглянуто Указ Президента України «Про Цілі сталого розвитку України на період до 2030 року» і визначено, що у вітчизняному законодавчому полі фінансова політика спрямована на впровадження цілей сталого розвитку, що регламентуються.

Встановлено, що усього в законодавчій базі даних України із загальної сукупності нормативно-правових актів у обсязі 243581 од. налічується лише 27 документів так чи інакше пов'язаних із розвитком, що ґрунтується на сталості. У більшості випадків ці Закони пов'язані із розробленням заходів щодо захисту Карпат та розвитку туризму, а тому можна стверджувати, що у цій сфері наше законодавство є недосконалим та вимагає доопрацювання. Зокрема, на думку авторів, не вистачає затвердженої обґрунтованої фінансової частини сталого розвитку держави.

Обґрунтовано важливість і значимість міжнародної складової нормативно-правового поля у сфері сталого розвитку, оскільки Україна є членом Паризької Угоди і у 2018 році подала до Секретаріату Рамкової конвенції Організації Об'єднаних Націй «Про зміну клімату» «Стратегію низьковуглецевого розвитку України до 2050 року».

Авторами надано ряд рекомендацій та пропозицій, виконання яких дасть можливість вирішити більшість проблем, що гальмують перехід до сталого розвитку та стримують реалізацію потенціалу економіки держави.

Результати проведених досліджень свідчать про те, що «Концепція сталого розвитку України» є на часі, вона цілком узгоджується із сучасними світовими і вітчизняними трансформаційними тенденціями та підвищує спроможність вирішення питань, пов'язаних з інтеграційними прагненнями України до вступу в Європейський Союз.

Abstract

The article examines the current state of implementation of the "Concept of Sustainable Development of Ukraine". It emphasizes the importance of this Concept as a determinant in the development and adaptation of the Ukrainian economy to the requirements of the world market in order to increase competitiveness and acquire signs of sustainability.

The publication considers the Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the Sustainable Development Goals of Ukraine until 2030" and states that in the domestic legislative field, financial policy is aimed at implementing the regulated goals of sustainable development.

It is established that in total in the legislative database of Ukraine from the general set of normative legal acts in the amount of 243581 units. there are only 27 documents in one way or another related to sustainability-based